

Music Representation for Analysis using Data Mining

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Abstract

Music analysis, i.e. using computers to analyze fully notated pieces of musical score, is one of the most important research issues in computer music. Machine learning has played a crucial role in the computer music almost since its beginning. Recently, research in the field has focused on music mining. Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining techniques. Data mining techniques are good candidates for music analysis. However, a proper music representation scheme is a prerequisite for their application. In this paper, we propose such a scheme for monophonic music representation as traditional data sets suitable for common data mining algorithms. We also present experimental results that demonstrate how the proposed representation technique is useful and helpful for analyzing and understanding music.

Keywords: Music representation, Data Mining

1 Introduction

In this paper, music analysis is considered as using computers to analyze fully notated pieces of musical score. Alternatively, music analysis could be considered as using computers to analyze performed and recorded music. Of course, the latter could be transformed to the former (the Automatic Music Transcription problem).

Artificial Intelligence was early related to music analysis within the computer music field. A lot of AI methodologies applied to music analysis as mathematical models, genetic algorithms, neural networks, hybrid systems and machine learning - symbolic systems. Machine learning tasks, like classification, prediction, forecasting, and the extraction of patterns and regularities from data, were early used both in music practice and in music research [32]. Example applications in music practice are reactive instruments, artificial performers that interact with human performers, adaptive music editing or composition systems, trainable optical notation recognition systems, automatic classification and characterization of styles, authors or music performers, etc. In music research, the musicological investigations are based primarily on the study of corpora of existing music data. Thus, especially in music research, data analysis and knowledge discovery capabilities of machine learning methods are proved very promising, supporting the human analyst in finding patterns and regularities in collections of real data.

In music, as in most of other fields of application, machine learning is adopted through inductive learning algorithms where concepts are learnt from positive and negative examples. Musical scores, as examples, have been also used as input to artificial neural networks, in order to learn habitual characteristics within compositions [21]. There are also some attempts based on analytical learning, as Explanation Based Learning [33] where the learning system is provided with music knowledge in order to guide the learning process.

Moreover, there have been numerous attempts to describe music in more or less grammatical terms. The idea common to all of these approaches is that in music a grammatical formalism may be used to give a finite (and therefore manageable) description of an infinite (and therefore intractable) set of structures. However, in such cases, there are arguments against using the notion of meaning/semantics in music, as linguistics and logicians do for their fields (e.g. [36]).

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks.

Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas. Decision trees, "if-then" rules and neural networks are the most popular such schemas. A lot of algorithms have been proposed in the literature for extracting classification rules from large relational databases, such as symbolic learning algorithms including decision trees algorithms (e.g. C4.5 [23]) and rule based algorithms (e.g. CN2 [8]), connectionist learning algorithms (e.g. back-propagation networks [27]), instance-based algorithms (e.g. PEBLS [9]) and hybrid algorithms (e.g. [3]).

Association rules can be used to represent frequent patterns in data, in the form of dependencies among concepts-attributes. In this paper, we consider the special case, that is known as the *the market basket problem*, where concepts-attributes represent products and the initial database is a set of customer purchases (transactions). This particular problem is well-studied in data mining. In this paper, we consider association rules of the form "90% of melodies that

include G also include E” (boolean association rules) (e.g [1, 4]). Formally, an association rule is a rule of the form $X \Rightarrow Y$, where X, Y named respectively antecedent and consequent of the rule and $X, Y \subset I = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_j\}$, such that $X \cap Y = \emptyset$ and $i_k, 1 \leq k \leq j$ is an item in the transaction database D . The informative power (named interestingness) of each association rule is measured by two indexes: the Support that measures the proportion of transactions in D containing both X and Y and the Confidence that measures the conditional probability of the consequent given the antecedent.

Clustering involves finding a specific number of subgroups (k) within a set of n observations (data points/objects); each described by d attributes. A clustering algorithm generates cluster descriptions and assigns each observation to one cluster (exclusive assignment) or in part to many clusters (partial assignment). Throughout this paper, we shall refer to the output of a clustering algorithm (e.g the medoids of the clusters) as clustering rules. Clustering methods have been widely studied in various scientific fields including Machine Learning, Neural Networks and Statistics. Clustering algorithms can be classified as either hierarchical or iterative (partitional, density search, factor analytic or clumping and graph theoretic). Complete-link, average link and single-link algorithms [11] are some popular hierarchical clustering algorithms. K -means [20], along with its variants (e.g. [19, 31]) are some popular partitional clustering algorithms.

In the literature, the term music data mining has been related to the application of machine learning algorithms [25, 35]. Machine learning and data mining algorithms differ in the input data. Machine learning algorithms use a small set of carefully selected data and could have the ability to interact with their environment, e.g. they could request new examples. Input data in data mining algorithms are large databases, (usually noisy and incomplete), while they cannot manipulate their environment.

In general, the application of artificial intelligence learning techniques to music analysis is based on either a Gestalt-based approach, where a predefined set of rules or principles is used, or on a memory-based approach, where a corpus of grouping structures of previously encountered musical pieces is used.

In listening to a piece of music, the human perceptual system segments the sequence of notes into groups or phrases that form a grouping structure for the whole piece. However, several different grouping structures may be compatible with a melody, i.e. a sequence of notes. Gestalt principles of proximity and similarity and the principle of melodic parallelism could be used for segmenting the melodies. If we wish to propose a memory-based approach to music as a serious alternative to a Gestalt-based approach, we should address the question of how any structure can be acquired if we do not have any structured pieces in our corpus to start with.

Data mining in music analysis aims at detecting, discovering, extracting or inducing of melodic or harmonic (sequential) patterns in given sets of composed or improvised works, (see [25] for a definition). Apart from mining music patterns forming traditional data sets, lately mining music patterns represented as data streams is also proposed [13].

In this paper we adopt a memory-based approach for music analysis, exploiting the benefits of data mining techniques. The effectiveness of data mining techniques does not heavily rely on the selection of input structure pieces. Thus, data mining techniques are good candidates for music analysis. However, a proper music representation scheme is a prerequisite for their application. In

this paper, we propose such a scheme for monophonic music representation as traditional data sets, suitable for common data mining algorithms. We also demonstrate both its efficiency and accuracy.

Little work has been done on the use of data mining association, classification and clustering algorithms in music analysis. In [28] the application of association rule mining is presented in order to find out the syntactic description of music style. The authors chose to represent chords in whole melody or in chorus, as a music feature that influence music style. Items, in input data set, are formed by either chords, or bi-grams: adjacent pairs of chords, or n-grams: a sequence of chords. Moreover, in [10] artificial neural networks, linear and Bayesian classifiers are used for the same problem. Also, the combination of rules extracted by ensemble of simple classifiers is used in [34], in order to extract rules covering the expressive music performance. In [22] a hierarchical clustering algorithm is used for music clustering based on key. In [17] clustering is applied to 88 Chinese Shanxi melodies from the city of Hequ and 30 German children songs from the Essen database to extract abstract motive sequences. Finally, clustering algorithms have been used for music performances.

In the rest of the paper we first describe the proposed music representation scheme (Section 2), then we present experimental results that demonstrate how the proposed scheme is useful and helpful for music analysis (Section 3), and finally we conclude (Section 4).

2 The proposed music representation scheme

Melodies should be represented in a multi-dimensional space. Examples of such dimensions are pitch, duration, dynamics and timbre. Almost all the relevant work, in the computer music literature, adopt pitch and duration as basic dimensions. Thus, as in most of music representation schemes proposed in the literature, we choose to represent these two acoustical music features. However, the proposed approach treats pitch and duration separately.

The proposed music representation scheme can be used for data mining analysis which aims at learning general patterns for both pitch and duration in certain music styles. Input data are melodies of musical pieces, i.e. sequences of notes. Note that we do not aim at a readable or user-friendly scheme, although the proposed scheme can be translated to such one.

The proposed scheme is not a general music representation scheme, (e.g. as that presented in [37]), which is abstract enough to be used for implementations of different tasks, (e.g. analysis, composition, etc), on different computer systems. General purpose representation scheme as well as most of music representation schemes (see [38] for an overview), even these based on recent approaches as XML [26], are not suitable for the commercial data mining algorithms. On the other hand, hierarchical music representation schemes (e.g. [15, 37] are not suitable for forming traditional data sets as input to data mining algorithms.

It is often hypothesised that a musical surface may be seen as a string of musical entities (e.g. [18]) such as notes, chords etc (see [7, 24] for an overview of the application of pattern processing algorithms on musical strings). Strings of musical entities impose different requirements to representation schemes [5, 7] with respect to data mining.

For instance, the proposed scheme adopts an absolute pitch representation.

Although most computer-aided musical applications adopt an absolute numeric pitch and duration representation, it is stated [7] that the absolute pitch encoding may be insufficient for applications in tonal music as it discards tonal qualities of pitches and pitch intervals, e.g. a tonal transportation from a major to minor key results in a different encoding of the musical passage and thus exact matches cannot detect the similarity between the two passages. Thus transpositions are not accounted for (e.g. the repeating pitch motive in bars 1 & 2 in Fig. 1, taken from [7]). Transposition is paramount in the understanding of musical patterns and pattern-matching and pattern-induction algorithms are developed primarily for sequences of pitch intervals [7]. However, association rule mining for instance, could extract the rule: $C\#,D \Rightarrow C$, if input data include sufficient number of identical to first bar in Fig. 1 bars. But such a rule, for various analysis purposes (e.g. composition or matching), could represent also the second bar in Figure 1 (after some preprocessing).

Figure 1: Beginning of theme of the A major sonata by Mozart

As another example, the proposed scheme does not adopt duration ratios. Thus, according to the proposed scheme, the rhythmic patterns shown in Fig. 2 (taken from [7]) do not match. Of course, one could argue that duration ratios could result in mismatching of the left rhythmic pattern in Fig. 2 to the one shown in Fig. 3, which is not true. Note that the proposed scheme represents duration in such a way that the latter rhythmic patterns match. The latter is confirmed also by an experiment in [14] investigating the splitting of durations, where the result is that the smaller the split ratio is, the larger is the measured similarity. On the other hand, association rule mining for instance, encourage the items in transactions to be sorted. This could not be achieved using duration ratios.

Figure 2: Rhythmic patterns matching at the level of duration ratios.

Figure 3: Rhythmic patterns matching at the level of duration ratios.

Thus, it is worth to note that the proposed scheme tries to satisfy data mining input requirements only.

2.1 Pitch representation

Pitch is a subjective sensation in which a listener assigns perceived tones to notes on a musical scale based mainly on the frequency of vibration, with a lesser relation to sound pressure level (loudness, volume). The pitch of a tone typically rises as frequency increases.

The proposed representation scheme is based on the measurement of the absolute values of the events in series. Moreover, consider that the source of melodies is a typical MIDI channel. In what follows we will describe pitch representation through an example application to the musical piece shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: An example musical piece.

When a musical piece is played on a MIDI instrument (midi keyboard or any midi controller) it transmits MIDI channel messages from its MIDI Out connector. A typical MIDI channel message sequence corresponding to a key being struck and released on a keyboard is: "When we press the middle C key (60) with a specific velocity (which is usually translated into the volume of the note) then the instrument sends one Note-On message". When we release the middle C key again with the possibility of velocity of release controlling some parameters, then the instrument sends one Note-Off message. Note-On and Note-Off are all channel messages. For the Note-On and Note-Off messages, the MIDI specification defines a number (from 0-127) for every possible note pitch (C, C#, D, etc.), and this number is included in the message.

Another information that we extract from the Midi Representation System is the Key_signature (`_KS`). This denotes the harmonic scale of the musical piece. It is kept for all the musical pieces in the input database, in order to be transposed in the same key. As mentioned in the previous section, the proposed scheme supports pitch processing within the same key. This piece of information for Key_signature is inserted in Database via msq file (variable `_KS`). Thus, input database initially includes a table with the form shown in Table 1 (with the help of msq files).

Then, each melody is segmented manually into fragments. A new table is included in the input database, in which a new line is created for each fragment, based on the primary line that has been imported by the msq file by name `midi_note`: [60,64,60,62,64,65,67,59,60] (removing the double entries in which velocity value = 0). Then, each fragment is further segmented into fragments that have the same melodic direction, i.e. either upwards or downwards, such as: [60,64],[64,60],[60,62,64,65,67],[67,59],[59,60].

For an efficient application of association rule mining algorithms, these fragments are sorted in ascending order. Moreover, a new column is added holding information about the melodic direction, i.e. ascending (1) or descending (0). Thus, the table for association rule mining, called "melody", is formed as in Table 2.

Table 1: Initial Table

	Line		midi_note	track_no	midi_file_id	velocity
...
7706	0 1 NON 1 60 42		60	1	45	42
7707	16 1 NON 1 64 87		64	1	45	87
7708	24 1 NON 1 60 68		60	1	45	68
7709	32 1 NON 1 62 78		62	1	45	78
7710	48 1 NON 1 64 80		64	1	45	80
7711	56 1 NON 1 65 83		65	1	45	83
7712	63 1 NON 1 67 50		67	1	45	50
...

Table 2: Table “melody”

	id	direction	note	note	note	note
...
T1	1	60	64			
T2	0	60	64			
T3	1	60	62	64	65	67
T4	0	59	67			
T5	1	59	60			
...

Table 3: Table “melody_s”

id	direction	...	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	...
...
T1	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...
T2	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...
T3	0	...	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	...
T4	1	...	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	...
...

Table 4: Time intervals

64	Whole Note (1)
32	Half Note (2)
16	Quarter Note (4)
8	Quaver (8)
4	Semi Quaver (16)
2	Demi Semi Quaver (32)
1	Hemi Demi Semi Quaver (64)

For classification and clustering each final fragment is represented as a 128 dimensional binary vector, since each one of its notes corresponds to a number from 0 to 127 (`midi_note_number`). The existence of a specific note in a fragment is indicated by “1” while its absence by “0”. Moreover, a column is also added holding information about the melodic direction, i.e. ascending (1) or descending (0). Thus, the corresponding input table, called “`melody_s`” is formed as in Table 3.

2.2 Duration representation

Rhythm is the arrangement of sounds in time. Meter animates time in regular pulse groupings, called measures or bars. The time signature (variable `_TS`) or meter signature specifies how many beats are in a measure, and which value of written note is counted and felt as a single beat. Through increased stress and attack (and subtle variations in duration), particular tones may be accented. There are conventions in most musical traditions for a regular and hierarchical accentuation of beats to reinforce the meter.

The proposed representation scheme is based on the key idea to indicate which discrete values of time a rhythm event happens. Moreover, consider that the source of rhythm patterns is a typical MIDI channel. In what follows we will describe duration representation through an example.

According to MIDI Representation System, time intervals are defined by the variable `Ticks` value. First, we convert all the midi files with the value of `Ticks` equal to t , i.e., the number of ticks for “whole time”. For the analysis of rhythm patterns the maximum rhythmic length is assigned to i measures of “whole time”, namely until the value $t \times i$. The latter constraint is imposed by the data base management system used for the implementation. For example, if $t = 64$ we use the time intervals described in Table 4.

For association rule mining, rhythm patterns of extracted fragments described in the previous subsection are represented in the table of the database called “`rhythm`”, in which a new line is created for each melody final fragment. For example, setting $t = 64$ and $i = 2$, the table “`rhythm`” which is formed as in Table 5. Each final fragment is represented as a 128 dimensional binary vector.

For classification and clustering each final fragment is also represented as a 128 dimensional binary vector, since each time corresponds to a number of ticks. An event within a fragment is indicated by “1” while its absence by “0”. Thus, the corresponding input table, called “`rhythm_s`” is formed as in Table 6.

Table 5: Table “rhythm”

...	...																	
T1	0	16	24	32	48	56	63	79	96									
...	...																	

Table 6: Table “rhythm_s”

id	0	...	16	...	24	...	32	...	48	...	56	...	63	...	79	...	96	...	
...
T1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
...

3 Experimental results

Collection of input data is an essential task, if the learning experiments are to produce new knowledge and insight into musical phenomena. Thus, input data should be unbiased realistic, contrary to preliminary experiments where input data were produced by the experimenter her/himself. Common data mining algorithms accept input data as tables.

Of course, a melodic segmentation technique [6] could be used in order to obtain input records. However, it is true that there is no a single correct segmentation of a musical piece. Moreover, since the construction of the training set is an off-line task, we used a manual segmentation for better control over input records [29].

As shown in [16], the clustering of melodic segments (used in Paradigmatic Analysis) is heavily relies on the used knowledge representation scheme and distance function.

Each melody is converted to a .msq file, using a midi score program (we used the Sibelius program). The .msq files are ASCII files with a specific structure that can be parsed. The .msq files were originally created by Siegfried Koepf and Bernd Haerpfer in 1998, needing a MIDI compatible computer system for algorithmic composition and score synthesis. A command line client parses .msq files and inserts the information it extracts in a database. This information can then be processed in various ways. A different command line client processes the database content and creates reports that can be fed in another client that generates rules using classification, clustering and association algorithms. All code is written using Java; the database is MySQL 5. Database connectivity is accomplished via JDBC.

Each .msq file contains a set of lines, separated with CRLF. Different lines contain different types of information. The application models the lines of interest with the MsqLine class. The following subclasses are implemented:

- MsqKsLine, which contains nformation about the music key signature in each music composition.

- MsqNonLine, which contains information about a note in the music composition (midi note, channel, duration, temporal instance of occurrence, etc).
- MsqTicksLine, which is a line that occurs once in an .msq file and declares the number of ticks for the composition.
- MsqTeLine, which contains information about the music style in each music composition.

Lines which cannot be parsed into one of the above are not considered of interest to the application and are ignored. MsqLineFactory is a singleton that parses a line to the appropriate MsqLine instance. The MsqFileParser parses an .msq file line by line and uses the MsqLineFactory to create meaningful content for the application. After a line has been parsed to an MsqLine subclass, DbConnector is used for inserting relevant data into the database. MsqDbDumper class orchestrates all the above, by iterating over all .msq files in a given directory and using MsqFileParser for parsing the files and inserting the information in the database. Each successfully processed file is archived in a timestamped archive directory. MsqExportHelper is the class that generates the report, by processing the data that has been inserted in the database. It generates the four previously mentioned files: melody, melody_s, rhythm and rhythm_s. melody and rhythm files are used for association rule mining while the rest are used for classification and clustering

The proposed system is tested in extracting data mining rules from a great number of melodies taken from Bach's Chorales (www.jsbchorales.net). As a technical result, the application of data mining algorithms seems very encouraging.

Extracted information can be used in several applications. For instance, given an input set of pitches/durations in a certain music style, an association rule indicates another set of pitches/durations which is similar to the input one. As another example of use, given a certain input pitch/duration in a certain music style, a classification rule indicates what pitches/durations can be combined with the input pitch/duration in this music style. Also, given an input set of pitches/durations in a certain music style, a clustering rule indicates another set of pitches/durations which is the most similar to the input set general representative (medoid) of this music style.

4 Conclusion

A symbolic music representation might be used [39] for recording (a record of some musical object, to be retrieved at a later date), analysis (to retrieve not the raw musical object, but some analyzed version) and generation/composition. In this paper, we present a new music representation scheme, demonstrating that it is suitable for recording and analysis.

We plan to extend the music features that the proposed scheme can represent to static (e.g. key, tempo) and thematic (e.g. chords) features. To this, we are currently working in extending the proposed music representation scheme in order to represent actual performances of melodies by human performers. Performances could be represented by tempo and loudness information. Thus, a data

mining analysis would provide general expression rules for the application of dynamics (crescendo vs. decrescendo) and tempo (accelerando vs. ritardando).

Moreover, we plan to use the proposed scheme in applications of data mining in other specific computer music problems: automatic generation of melodies, melodic segmentation, discovering repeated patterns and music performance recognition.

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Registration and opening ceremony

10.00-11.00 KEYNOTE SPEAKER

Byron Almén, Univerzitet Teksasa u Ostinu, SAD / *University of Texas at Austin, USA*
Narativni arhetipovi: teorija i analiza
Narrative Archetypes: Theory and Analysis

I Sesija / Session I Predsedava / *Chair* Byron Almén

11.15-11.45

Martin Eybl, Univerzitet za muziku i izvođačke umetnosti, Beč, Austrija / *Universität für Musik und Darstellende Kunst, Wien, Austria*
Da capo i repriza: ponavljanje u muzičkom narativu
Da Capo and Recapitulation: Repetition in Musical Narrative

11.45-12.15

Jeremy Barham, Univerzitet Sari, Guildford, V. Britanija / *University of Surrey, Guildford, Great Britain*
Rikerovske narativne strukture, kognitivni modeli XIX veka i „anksioznost dekadencije” u prvom stavu Malerove Treće simfonije

Ricoeurian Narrative Structures, 19th-Century Cognitive Models, and the 'Anxiety of Decadence' in the First Movement of Mahler's Third Symphony

12.15-12.30 pauza / *break*

12.30-13.00

Tijana Popović, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Šta mi priča *Pesma o zemlji* Gustava Malera

What Das Lied von der Erde tells me

13.00-13.30

Nataša Crnjanski, Akademija umetnosti, Novi Sad / *Academy of Arts, Novi Sad*

Metaforična muzika i muzička metafora

Metaphorical Music and Musical Metaphor

13.30-15.00 pauza za ručak / *lunch break*

II Sesija / *Session II* Predsedava / *Chair* Martin Eybl

15.00-15.30

Kalliopi Stiga, Muzikološki fakultet Univerziteta u Atini, Grčka / *Faculté de musicologie – Université d'Athènes, Greece*

Teodorakisovska narativna melodija u susretu s poetskim lirizmom

La mélodie narrative théodorakienne à la rencontre du lyrisme poétique;

15.30-16.00

Jelena Novak, Amsterdamska škola za analizu kulture, Univerzitet Amsterdama / *Amsterdam School for Cultural Analysis, University of Amsterdam*

Pripovedanje ponavljanjem: funkcija muzike u postoperskoj narativnosti

Narrating by Repeating: Function of Music in Post-operatic Narrativity

16.00-16.30

Wu Dongpan, Institut za tehnologiju Huang Ši, Kina / *Huangshi Institute of Technology, China*

Prefinjeni *Qing Sheng* i graciozni *Ce Sheng* – analiza kompozicije *Duan Qing*

Exquisite Qing Sheng and Graceful Ce Sheng – Analysis of Duan Qing in qin qu Ji Shi Si Nong;

16.30-17.00 pauza / *break*

17.00-17.30

Ivana Perković, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Bitka u balskoj dvorani? Ekspresivni zanrovi u Mozartovoj kontradanci La Bataille KV 535;

Battle in the Ballroom? Expressive Genres in Mozart's Contredance La Bataille K 535

17.30-18.00

Ana Stefanović, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Još jednom o muzičkim „topicima“ i analizi stila

Once more on musical “ topics ” and style analysis

18.00 Koktel / *Coctail*

20.30 – 21.30 Fakultet muzičke umetnosti / *Faculty of Music* Kralja Milana 50

Koncert / *Concert*

Srpska kamerna muzika / *Serbian chamber music*

Klasa kamernе muzike profesora Gorana Marinkovića / *Chamber Music class of Professor Goran Marinković*

SUBOTA, 16. MAJ, 2009 / *Saturday, May 16, 2009*

Univerzitet umetnosti / *University of Arts, Kosančićev venac, 29*

III Sesija / *Session III* Predsedava / *Chair* Nico Schuler

10.00-10.30

Luca Bruno, Odsek za komunikacije, Univerzitet Kalabrije, Italija / *Dipartimento di Comunicazione e D.A.M.S., Università della Calabria, Italy.*

Harmonija i postavka teksta u delu *Canzone villanesche alla napolitana* Adriana Vilterta (1542-1545)

Harmony and Text Setting in Adrian Willaert's Canzone villanesche alla napolitana (1542-1545)

10.30-11.00

Théodora Psychoyou, Univerzitet Pariz IV - Sorbona / *Université Paris IV - Sorbonne*

Kakav zakon za *énergie des modes*? Percepcija i racionalizacija izražajnih svojstava muzike u francuskoj muzičkoj misli XVII veka

What statute for the énergie des modes? Perception and rationalization of expressive properties of music in 17th-century French musical thought

11.00-11.30

Miloš Zatkalik, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Može li se Doktor Džekil pomiriti s Mister Hajdom: tonalnost i pripitomljeni tonski nizovi u Dvanaestom gudačkom kvartetu Dmitrija Šostakoviča

Can Dr. Jekyll Be Reconciled with Mr. Hyde: Tonality and Domesticated Tone-Rows in Dmitri Shostakovich's Twelfth String Quartet

11.30-12.00 pauza / *break*

IV Sesija / *Session IV* Predsedava / *Chair* Miloš Zatkalik

12.00-12.30

Denis Collins, Univerzitet Kvinslenda, Brizbejn, Australija / *The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia:*

Henri Persl: tri deonice nad ostinatom i tradicija engleskog kontrapunkta

Henry Purcell's Three Parts Upon a Ground and the Traditions of English Counterpoint

12.30-13.00

Zoran Božanić, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Ispoljavanje skrivene polifonije na primeru Bahovih svita za solo violončelo

Manifestations of Hidden Polyphony in Bach's Suites for Unaccompanied Cello

13.00-13.30

Senka Belić, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*
Hristovo rođenje i dvohorski *canon multiplex*: motet *Nesciens mater virgo virum* Žana Mutona
Birth of Jesus Christ and Double-Chorus canon multiplex: Motet Nesciens mater virgo virum by Jean Mouton

13.30-14.00

Predrag Repanić, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*
Primena tehnike pomerajućih kontrapunkta u radu sa osnovnom temom iz ciklusa *Umetnost fuge*
J. S. Baha
Application of the Movable Counterpoint Technique in Working with the Principal Subject of J. S. Bach's The Art of the Fugue

14.00-15.00 pauza za ručak / *lunch break*

V Sesija / Session V Predsedava / Chair Denis Collins

15.00-15.30

Andreas Holzer, Univerzitet za muziku i izvođačke umetnosti, Beč, Austrija / *Universität für Musik und Darstellende Kunst, Wien, Austria*
Forma: pledoaje za jednu zanemarenu kategoriju
Form: Ein Plädoyer für eine vernachlässigte Kategorie

15.30-16.00

Dimitar Ninov, Državni univerzitet Teksasa, San Markos, SAD / *Texas State University, San Marcos, USA*
Nezavisna fraza, univerzalna rečenica i grupe fraza: predlog klasifikacije strukturnih ekvivalenata jednodielne forme
The Independent Phrase, the Universal Sentence and the Phrase Group: Suggested Classification of Structures Equivalent to a One-Part Form

16.00-16.30

Danijela Zdravić Mihajlović, Fakultet umetnosti, Niš / *Faculty of Arts, Niš*
Razmatranje muzičke rečenice i perioda u literaturi ruskih, bugarskih, makedonskih i srpskih autora (Mazelj, Stojanov, Bužarovski, Peričić, Mihajlović, Čavlović, Popović, Zatkalik, Sabo)
Consideration of the Musical Sentence and Period by Russian, Bulgarian, Macedonian and Serbian Authors (Mazel', Stoyanov, Bužarovski, Peričić, Mihajlović, Čavlović, Popović, Zatkalik, Sabo)

16.30-17.00 pauza / *break*

VI Sesija / Session VI Predsedava / Chair Dimitar Ninov

17.00-17.30

Nico Schuler, Državni univerzitet Teksasa, San Markos, SAD / *Texas State University, San Marcos, USA*
Razvoj kompjuterske tehnologije i njen uticaj na razvoj muzičko-analitičkih metoda
The Development of Computing Technology and Its Influence on the Development of Music-Analytical Methods

17.30-18.00

C. Halkiopoulos, Univerzitet Patrasa, Grčka / *University of Patras, Greece*

B. Boutsinas, Univerzitet Patrasa, Grčka / *University of Patras, Greece*

Predstavljanje muzike za analizu korišćenjem tehnike *data mining*

Music Representation for Analysis Using Data Mining

20.00 večera (fakultativno) / *dinner* (optional)

NEDELJA, 17. MAJ, 2009 / *Sunday, May 17, 2009*

Univerzitet umetnosti / *University of Arts, Kosančićev venac, 29*

VII Sesija / *Session VII*

Predsedava / *Chair* Andreas Holzer

10.00-10.30

Jasna Veljanovic-Ranković, Filološko-umetnički fakultet, Kragujevac / *Faculty of Philology and Arts, Kragujevac*

Francuske svite J. S. Baha: predlog tipologije baroknog dvodela;

J. S. Bach's French Suites: A Proposition for the Typology of Binary Form

10.30-11.00

Anica Sabo, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Oblik varijacija – koraci u analitičkoj proceduri;

Variation Form – Steps in Analytical Procedure

11.00-11.30

Eduardo Abrantes, Novi lisabonski univerzitet, Portugal / *New University of Lisbon, Portugal*

Beznačajni glasovi – fenomenologija vokalne improvizacije i odsustvo značenja

Insignificant Voices – the Phenomenology of Vocal Improvisation and Meaninglessness

11.30-12.00 pauza / *break*

12.00-12.30

Sonja Marinković, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Tretman Glinkinih varijacija u Baladi Finca;

The Treatment of Glinka's Variations in the Finn's Ballad

12.30-13.00

Mirjana Živković, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Svite iz baleta *Ohridska legenda* – potraga za njihovim identitetima

(povodom 50 godina od smrti Stevana Hristića)

Suites from the Ballet The Legend of Ohrid by Stevan Hristić – A Quest for Their Identities (on the 50th Anniversary of Stevan Hristić's Death)

13.00-14.30 pauza za ručak / *lunch break*

VIII Sesija / Session VIII Predsedava / Chair Mirjana Živković

14.30-15.00

Marko Aleksić, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Završni monolog Salome u istoimenoj muzičkoj drami Riharda Štrausa: sistem harmonskih simbolizacija

Salome's Final Monologue in Richard Strauss's Opera: The System of Harmonic Symbolization

15.00-15.30

Srdan Teparić, Fakultet muzičke umetnosti, Beograd / *Faculty of Music, Belgrade*

Tonalnost u funkciji stila u klavirskoj sviti *Kuprenov grob* Morisa Ravela

Tonality as a Function of Style in the Piano Suite Le tombeau de Couperin by Maurice Ravel

15.30-16.00 pauza / break

16-16.30

Atila Sabo, Filološko-umetnički fakultet, Kragujevac / *Faculty of Philology and Arts, Kragujevac*

Odnos melodije i harmonije u horskim kompozicijama zasnovanim na folklornom uzorku

Relationships between Melody and Harmony in Choral Compositions Based on Folklore

16.30-17.00

Filip Pavličić, Filološko-umetnički fakultet, Kragujevac / *Faculty of Philology and Arts, Kragujevac*

Harmonski sklopovi u kompoziciji Rondo sekvenca Mirjane Živković

Harmonic Configurations in Rondo Sequence by Mirjana Živković

17.00-18.00

zaključci / *conclusions*